

How to Cite (APA): Beraldi, P., et al. (2025). Optimal design of hybrid multigeneration systems through cvar-based risk-averse programming. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 288–297). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

Optimal Design of Hybrid Multigeneration Systems Through CVaR-Based Risk-Averse Programming

Patrizia Beraldi¹, Nazmi Sener^{1,2} and Angelo Algieri¹

¹ Department of Mechanical, Energy and Management Engineering, University of Calabria, Cosenza, Italy
patrizia.beraldi@unical.it, angelo.algieri@unical.it

² Department of Industrial Engineering, Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University, Antalya, Türkiye
nazmi.sener@alanya.edu.tr

KEYWORDS - Polygeneration, Energy Management, Sizing, Risk Aversion.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a risk-averse stochastic programming framework for the optimal design of hybrid multigeneration energy systems, integrating renewable-based technologies, advanced storage solutions, and green fuel-powered devices. The approach incorporates Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) to address uncertainties in energy demand, renewable generation, and market price fluctuations, supporting robust decision-making under uncertain and potentially adverse conditions. By considering CVaR, the framework aims to enhance system resilience by accounting for both expected performance and the potential impact of rare, high-cost events. The model unifies strategic planning for system configuration and capacity with operational management, formulating a comprehensive optimization problem that reflects the complexities of modern energy systems. Detailed modeling of energy conversion processes, storage dynamics, and system interactions is included to ensure realistic and practical solutions. The proposed framework is adaptable to a wide range of scenarios and risk preferences, providing a balanced approach to efficiency, sustainability, and risk management. This research contributes to the advancement of sustainable energy system design by offering a practical methodology for integrating diverse energy resources and managing uncertainty, ultimately supporting the development of resilient and economically viable hybrid multigeneration energy infrastructures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global energy landscape is undergoing a profound transformation, driven by the urgent need to mitigate climate change, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and transition away from fossil fuels [1], [2]. In response, international policy frameworks such as the European Green Deal have set ambitious targets, including a 55% reduction in emissions by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050 [3]. Achieving these goals requires not only the deployment of renewable energy technologies but also the development of integrated, flexible, and resilient energy systems capable of managing the variability and uncertainty inherent in renewable sources.

Hybrid multigeneration systems, also known as polygeneration or multi-energy systems, have emerged as a promising solution to these challenges. These systems integrate multiple energy conversion technologies, such as combined heat and power (CHP) units, boilers, chillers, photovoltaic (PV) panels, and solar thermal collectors, within a centralized infrastructure [4], [5]. By simultaneously producing electricity, heating, and cooling, they enable efficient resource utilization and cost-effective energy management [6]. The inclusion of renewable energy sources and green fuels, such as biomass, enhances environmental sustainability, while advanced storage technologies help buffer the intermittency of renewables [7], [8].

Despite their potential, the design and operation of hybrid multigeneration systems are inherently complex. Decision-makers must evaluate a wide array of technologies and configurations, considering factors such as temporal demand profiles, resource availability, fuel prices, and market dynamics [4], [9]. The stochastic nature of renewable generation and energy demand further complicates this process, necessitating the use of advanced optimization techniques that can account for uncertainty and risk.

Recent research has increasingly focused on the development of robust and risk-averse optimization frameworks to address these challenges [4], [10]. Hybrid energy systems that combine PV, battery storage systems (BSS), and conventional generators have demonstrated improved reliability and efficiency. However, their performance is highly sensitive to fluctuations in renewable output and load demand, which can lead to operational inefficiencies and increased costs if not properly managed [11], [12]. Diesel generators are often used as backup sources to ensure reliability [13], [14], while BSS enables surplus PV energy to be stored and dispatched during periods of low generation, enhancing system flexibility and resilience [15]. A recent study by Beraldi et al. [16] demonstrates that hybrid multigeneration configurations can simultaneously minimize cost and greenhouse-gas emissions in the residential sector.

The literature highlights the importance of incorporating uncertainty into both the design and operational phases of hybrid systems. Studies by Nojavan et al. [17] and Sharafi et al. [18] show that stochastic modeling improves economic performance and system robustness. Similarly, Pali et al. [19] and Li et al. [20] emphasize the critical role of storage integration and optimal sizing under uncertainty. Probabilistic and techno-economic optimization approaches have been shown to enhance the viability of hybrid systems, particularly in off-grid and microgrid applications [15], [21].

Among the various risk-aware optimization methods, CVaR has gained prominence for its ability to capture tail risks and extreme events [22], [23], [24]. Unlike traditional variance-based or risk-neutral models, CVaR explicitly quantifies expected losses in the worst-case scenarios, offering a more comprehensive view of risk exposure [25], [26]. This is particularly valuable in energy systems where financial volatility and operational disruptions can have significant consequences [27], [28]. The integration of CVaR into energy system optimization has been shown to support more robust investment decisions and enhance system reliability under uncertainty [20].

Despite these advances, there remains a need for integrated frameworks that jointly address strategic planning and operational management in hybrid multigeneration systems. Most existing models either focus on deterministic optimization or treat investment and operational decisions separately, limiting their ability to capture the full complexity of real-world systems. Moreover, while CVaR has been applied in various energy contexts, its application to multi-energy systems with detailed component-level modeling remains limited.

This study addresses these gaps by proposing a comprehensive CVaR-based stochastic programming framework for the optimal design and operation of hybrid multigeneration systems. The model integrates investment and operational decisions, incorporates detailed representations of energy conversion and storage technologies, and explicitly accounts for uncertainty in demand, renewable generation, and market prices. By doing so, it provides a practical and adaptable tool for designing resilient, efficient, and sustainable energy infrastructures.

The main contributions of this work are threefold: (1) the development of an integrated stochastic programming model that captures both strategic and operational aspects of hybrid system design, (2) the incorporation of CVaR-based risk measures to manage uncertainty and support robust decision-making, and (3) the demonstration of the model’s effectiveness through case studies that highlight trade-offs between cost efficiency and risk resilience.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the detailed modeling framework, including system components and mathematical formulation. Section 3 introduces the case study, outlining the data settings and scenario generation process. Section 4 discusses computational results, highlighting the benefits of incorporating risk aversion in system design. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study with key findings and suggestions for future research directions.

2 PROBLEM DEFINITION AND MODEL FORMULATION

We consider the problem of designing an integrated energy system to satisfy the electricity, heating and cooling demand of a residential complex. Solar energy is captured through PV for electricity and solar thermal collectors (STC) for heating. Since solar output varies, CHP fueled by biomass provides both electricity and heat, especially during periods of low solar generation. Biomass boilers (BB) serve as an additional backup for heating needs. To satisfy cooling demand, the system uses both electric chillers (EC) and absorption chillers (AC). ECs deliver rapid cooling using electricity, while ACs utilize surplus heat from CHPs, maximizing energy use. Advanced storage solutions—BSS, and hot energy storage (HES) and cooling energy storage (CES)—buffer fluctuations in supply and demand, ensuring energy is available when needed. All components are interconnected via a distribution network, allowing efficient energy transfer, waste heat recovery, and flexible allocation based on real-time demand. The visual representation of the system is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Graphical Representation of the System

The objective is to determine the optimal configuration of the integrated system by selecting the appropriate combination and sizing of technologies to minimize total costs while ensuring reliable energy supply. This involves a careful balance between capital investment, operational efficiency, and system flexibility. The optimization must account for the temporal variability of energy demand and renewable generation, as well as the interactions among system components. For instance, the use of surplus heat from CHPs in ACs not only reduces electricity consumption but also enhances overall system efficiency. Similarly, the coordinated operation of storage units allows for load shifting and peak shaving, reducing dependency on external supplies.

To capture the inherent uncertainty in renewable output, fuel prices, and demand profiles, the problem is formulated by the stochastic programming framework. Uncertain parameters are

represented by random variables are defined on a given probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) . Under the assumption of discrete distribution, we consider a given number of scenarios defined by subscript ω , and we denote by p_ω the corresponding probability of occurrence. This approach enables the evaluation of multiple future scenarios, ensuring that the selected system configuration performs robustly under a wide range of conditions. Furthermore, to mitigate the risk of high-cost outcomes, the model incorporates CVaR as a risk measure, guiding the solution toward configurations that are not only cost-effective on average, but also resilient to adverse events.

Figure 2 illustrates the CvaR defined starting from the companion measure Value-at-Risk (VaR). While the VaR represents the highest lost that can be observed with a confidence level α , the CVaR focuses on the worst $1-\alpha$ share of possible outcomes, which is shaded in orange and represents the average cost (or loss) of those extreme scenarios that exceed VaR. In contrast, the distribution center of mass corresponds to the expectation, which weighs every outcome by its probability. Taken together, the picture shows that the expectation gauges overall performance, while CVaR zeroes in on the average severity of the worst cases, making it a more targeted measure for understanding downside risk in energy-system planning.

Figure 2: Graphical Representation of CVaR

The mathematical model for the optimal design and operation of a hybrid multi-energy system is constructed to capture the interplay between investment decisions, operational scheduling, and risk management, with a particular focus on the discrete nature of PV panels and STC as integer assets.

The selection of technologies is governed by the constraint that at most one technology can be chosen from each group, except for PV and STC:

$$\sum_{i \in N_j} x_{ij} \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in J - PV, STC \quad (1)$$

The installed capacity for each technology is linked to the selection variables by:

$$y_j = \sum_{i \in N_j} S_{ij} x_{ij} \quad \forall j \in J - PV, STC \quad (2)$$

For PV and STC, the model determines the number of units to install, subject to the available area constraint:

$$l_{PV} n_{PV} + l_{STC} n_{STC} \leq L \quad (3)$$

where l_{PV} and l_{STC} are the areas required per unit of PV and STC, and L is the total available area. Both PV and STC are required to be non-negative integers:

$$n_{PV} \in \mathbb{Z}^+, n_{STC} \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (4)$$

Each feasible configuration corresponds to a specific operational plan that must fulfill energy requirements while respecting technical constraints. These plans are adaptable to different scenarios, denoted by ω . For every hour h of day d , several key decisions are made.

The status of each power generator—CHP, BB, AC, and EC—is represented by $q_j^{hd\omega}$, where a value of 1 indicates the device is on, and 0 means it is off. The energy output from each device, $P_{hd\omega}^j$, is determined as a linear function of its efficiency μ_j and the fuel consumed $B_{hd\omega}^j$. This is calculated

in detail at Beraldi et al. [16]. For CHP units, which supply both electricity and heat, heat production is tracked by $P_{hd\omega}^{CHPH}$. Chillers within the system may be powered by either electricity (EC) or heat (AC) generated internally.

The management of storage systems—BES, HES, and CES—is described by the variables $SC_{hd\omega}^j$ for state of charge, $I_{hd\omega}^j$ for energy charged, and $O_{hd\omega}^j$ for energy discharged. Market participation is captured by $PG_{hd\omega}^+$, representing electricity purchased, and $PG_{hd\omega}^-$, representing electricity sold back to the grid. The contribution from PV and STC is determined by the number of units installed and their scenario-dependent production factors, $\xi_{hd\omega}^{PV}$ and $\xi_{hd\omega}^{STC}$.

Unmet heat and cooling demands are represented as $R_{hd\omega}^H$, and $R_{hd\omega}^C$, respectively. The total demand for electricity, heat and cooling are shown as $D_{hd\omega}^E$, as $D_{hd\omega}^H$, and as $D_{hd\omega}^C$, respectively. This framework ensures that, regardless of the scenario, the system can adjust its operation to reliably meet energy demands and comply with all technical requirements.

The operational status variable $q_j^{hd\omega}$ for technology j at hour h , day d , and scenario ω can only be active if the technology is selected.

$$q_j^{hd\omega} \leq \sum_{i \in N_j} x_{ij} \quad j = \{CHP, BB, AC, EC\} \quad (5)$$

Additional constraints ensure that each power device operates within its technical limits. These conditions require that, whenever a device is active, its energy output remains between specified minimum and maximum levels. $P_{hd\omega}^j$ represents the produced energy amount from technology j at hour h of the day d for scenario ω . These bounds depend on the device's capacity, denoted by y_j , and are determined using device-specific coefficients Υ_j . In summary, these technical requirements are formulated as:

$$\Upsilon_j y_j q_j^{hd\omega} \leq P_{hd\omega}^j \leq y_j q_j^{hd\omega} \quad j = \{CHP, BB, AC, EC\} \quad (6)$$

Further clarification is necessary for certain components. Notably, the CHP unit generates both electricity and heat. As a result, extra constraints are applied to limit the amount of heat produced, represented by $P_{hd\omega}^{CHPH}$:

$$\Upsilon_{CHP} \psi y^{CHP} q_{hd\omega}^{CHP} \leq P_{hd\omega}^{CHPH} \leq \psi y^{CHP} q_{hd\omega}^{CHP} \quad (7)$$

where ψ represents the relationship between thermal efficiency and the electrical efficiency of the CHP system.

For chillers, the energy input comes from both electricity and thermal sources available within the system. The electricity required to operate EC, represented by $CL_{hd\omega}^{EC}$, can originate from the CHP, PV, energy released from BES, or electricity purchased from the grid. In the case of AC, it is powered by heat supplied by CHP, BB, STC, or HES. The total heat delivered to the AC is denoted by $CL_{hd\omega}^{AC}$. These variables, $CL_{hd\omega}^{EC}$ and $CL_{hd\omega}^{AC}$, are incorporated into the demand balance constraints for the respective energy types, ensuring that the system's supply meets the requirements for each commodity:

$$P_{hd\omega}^{CHP} + \xi_{hd\omega}^{PV} n_{PV} + O_{hd\omega}^{BES} + PG_{hd\omega}^+ = D_{hd\omega}^E + I_{hd\omega}^{BES} + PG_{hd\omega}^- + CL_{hd\omega}^{EC} \quad (8)$$

$$P_{hd\omega}^{CHPH} + P_{hd\omega}^{BB} + \xi_{hd\omega}^{STC} n_{STC} + O_{hd\omega}^{HES} + R_{hd\omega}^H = D_{hd\omega}^H + I_{hd\omega}^{HES} + CL_{hd\omega}^{AC} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{hd\omega}^{EC} + P_{hd\omega}^{AC} + O_{hd\omega}^{CES} + R_{hd\omega}^C = D_{hd\omega}^C + I_{hd\omega}^{CES} \quad (10)$$

Eqs. (11), (12) and (13) represent electric, heat and cooling balance equations, respectively. The constraints governing storage devices share a common structure, differing only in the loss coefficients, denoted as γ_j , which are specific to each type of storage. It's also important to mention that the TESC unit is operational solely during the summer period. The detailed form of these constraints is presented below.

$$SC_{hd\omega}^j = SC_{h-1d\omega}^j + \gamma_j I_{hd\omega}^j - \frac{O_{hd\omega}^j}{\gamma_j} \quad \forall d, \forall h \geq 2 \quad (11)$$

$$SC_{hd\omega}^j = \phi_j \gamma_j + \gamma_j I_{hd\omega}^j - \frac{O_{hd\omega}^j}{\phi_j} \quad \forall d, h = 1 \quad (12)$$

$$SC_{|H|d\omega}^j = \phi_j \gamma_j \quad (13)$$

Eqs. (14) and (15) describe how the storage system's state of charge changes between periods, based on the energy charged and discharged. At the start of the day, the initial state of charge is set according to the selected storage size (15), while (16) ensures the storage returns to this initial level by the end of the day. The model also limits the maximum stored energy (17), as well as the rates of charging (18) and discharging (19), all as functions of the storage size y_j and the coefficients ϕ_j and β_j . These constraints collectively ensure the storage system operates within its designed capacity and performance limits.

$$\phi_j \gamma_j \leq SC_{hd\omega} \leq y_j \quad (14)$$

$$I_{hd\omega}^j \leq \beta_j \gamma_j \quad (15)$$

$$O_{hd\omega}^j \leq \beta_j \gamma_j \quad (16)$$

The annual operating and management (z_ω) costs are calculated based on three primary factors: fuel used by power generation units, electricity purchased from the grid, and maintenance expenses for storage systems. These total costs are offset by any income earned from selling surplus energy back to the grid. Specifically, for each scenario ω , these costs are determined as follows:

$$z_\omega = \sum_{d \in D} \theta_d \sum_{h \in H} \sum_{j=CHP}^{BB} CF_{hd\omega}^j B_{hd\omega}^j + \sum_{d \in D} \theta_d \sum_{h \in H} (CP_{hd\omega}^+ PG_{hd\omega}^+ - CP_{hd\omega}^- PG_{hd\omega}^-) + \sum_{d \in D} \theta_d \sum_{h \in H} \sum_{j=BES, HES}^{CES} (c I_{hd\omega}^j + c O_{hd\omega}^j) + \sum_{d \in D} \theta_d \sum_{h \in H} c_p (R_{hd\omega}^H + R_{hd\omega}^C)$$

Here, $CF_{hd\omega}^j$ denotes the fuel price for device j at hour h on day d under scenario ω . The terms $CP_{hd\omega}^+$ and $CP_{hd\omega}^-$ correspond to the costs of purchasing and selling electricity, respectively. The final terms capture the expenses related to charging and discharging storage systems. Additionally, c represents the penalty cost for utilizing storage, while c_p is the penalty cost incurred for unmet energy demand.

In the proposed model In designing a hybrid multi-energy system, the objective is to minimize the risk-adjusted total cost using a CVaR approach. This method ensures the solution is robust against high-cost scenarios by focusing on the tail of the cost distribution. CVaR at a confidence level, denoted by α , is minimized and is represented by the sum of an auxiliary variable (VaR), η , and the average of the excess costs, ζ_ω , across all scenarios ω in the set Ω . CVaR is formalized as follows:

$$CVaR_\alpha(z) = \eta + \frac{1}{(1-\alpha)} \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} p_\omega \zeta_\omega$$

The defining conditions for ζ_ω are:

$$\zeta_\omega \geq z_\omega - \eta, \quad \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (17)$$

$$\zeta_\omega \geq 0, \quad \forall \omega \in \Omega \quad (18)$$

Eqs. (17)–(18) collectively force ζ_ω to coincide with $\max\{0, z_\omega - \eta\}$ for every scenario $\omega \in \Omega$. Specifically, (17) obliges ζ_ω to cover any shortfall of η whenever the scenario cost z_ω exceeds that benchmark, while (18) rules out negative values so that ζ_ω remains a non-negative penalty.

The model's objective is to minimize the total system cost, which includes investment costs for all technologies, operational costs such as fuel and electricity purchases, and a risk term based on CVaR to account for cost uncertainty. The objective function is expressed as:

$$\min[\sum_{j \in J} C_j y_j + C_{PV} n_{PV} + C_{STC} n_{STC} + (1 - \lambda) \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} p_{\omega} z_{\omega} + \lambda(\text{CVaR}_{\alpha}(z))] \quad (19)$$

where C_j , C_{PV} , and C_{STC} are the investment costs for each technology, PV, and STC, respectively, the expectation is taken over all scenarios ω in the set Ω , λ is the risk coefficient, and z_{ω} is the recourse of the model.

The nonlinearity introduced by the product of first- and second-stage variables in constraints (9) and (10) is managed by defining new variables for each generation device—CHP, BB, AB, and EC—such that $k_{hd\omega}^j = y_j q_j^{hd\omega}$. This results in an increased number of variables and constraints, as the following conditions must be enforced for every hour, day, and scenario:

$$k_{hd\omega}^j \leq y_j \quad (20)$$

$$k_{hd\omega}^j \leq L_j q_j^{hd\omega} \quad (21)$$

$$k_{hd\omega}^j \geq y_j - L_j(1 - q_j^{hd\omega}) \quad (22)$$

Here, L_j is chosen as the maximum possible size for each generation technology, which helps maintain computational efficiency while ensuring the constraints are properly enforced.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

3.1 Data Settings

A real-world case study was conducted for a residential complex in Turin, Italy, comprising five buildings with a total of 100 apartments and a combined roof area of 2,500 m². To account for seasonal differences, the analysis used four representative days—one for each season—with hourly time steps.

Average daily energy demand profiles were established, and scenarios were generated using a normal distribution with a standard deviation of 20% from the mean. Electricity and wood biomass prices were based on Italian market data. Electricity purchase prices were derived from 2017–2023 data[29], while the selling price was set at 10.0 c€/kWh. Biomass fuel prices were calculated using historical data from the Italian Agroforestry Energy Association [30]. Solar energy production estimates were obtained using PVGIS, with irradiance statistics based on data from 2005 to 2020. Scenarios for solar output were generated using a truncated normal distribution. Technical specifications and purchase costs for all technologies in the system are detailed in Beraldi et al [16]. A preliminary market screening was performed to ensure that selected technologies meet both energy needs and spatial constraints.

Eligible sizes for all components are as follows: CHP ranges from 10 – 50 kW, BB spans 223 – 650 kW, EC varies between 9.2 – 75 kW, AC lies within 35 – 176 kW, HES stores 250 – 1 250 kWh, CES covers 500 – 2 000 kWh, and BSS extends from 40 – 120 kWh.

3.2 Results

Computational experiments were conducted on a laptop with an Intel Core i7-13650HX processor (2.60 GHz), 32 GB of RAM, and Windows 11. The optimization models were implemented and solved using Python (version 3.12.7) in combination with the commercial GUROBI solver (version 12.0.1). As this is a preliminary study, scenario size is fixed to 50 for all experiments.

Table 1 Optimally Selected Device Sizes

λ	α	CHP	BB	EC	AC	HES	CES	BSS	PV	STC
	0	20	351	32.3	70	1250	1000	60	419	63
1	0.7	20	351	9.2	105	1000	1000	60	382	92
1	0.8	20	495	52.7	70	1000	750	60	490	7
1	0.9	20	495	52.7	70	1000	750	80	499	0
	EEV	20	650	32.3	70	1000	500	80	499	0

Table 2 shows consistent risk-response progression. Switching from risk-neutral ($\lambda = 0$) to fully risk-averse ($\lambda = 1$) keeps CHP at 20 kW and HES near 1 MW but reallocates capacity toward electrical resilience: BB and AC expand or hold steady, EC shrinks, and both BSS and PV rise, enhancing flexibility without increasing total size. Within $\lambda = 1$, higher tail-risk aversion ($\alpha = 0.70 \rightarrow 0.80 \rightarrow 0.90$) fine-tunes rather than enlarge the system. At $\alpha = 0.70$ the mix mirrors the baseline; at $\alpha = 0.80$ BB jumps to 495 kW and PV to 490 kW while CES and STC contract; and at $\alpha = 0.90$ BSS grows, PV nearly maxes out, and STC disappears, prioritizing dispatchable and storage assets for extreme events. Thus, greater risk aversion redistributes capacity toward robust electric support while preserving the cost-efficient thermal core.

A preliminary set of experiments was carried out to assess the advantages of explicitly incorporating uncertainty into the decision-making process. To quantify this benefit, the Value of Stochastic Solution (VSS) was calculated, which is a standard measure in stochastic programming. The VSS indicates the percentage improvement achieved by using a stochastic approach compared to a deterministic one. Mathematically, the VSS is defined as:

$$VSS = (z_{RA} - z_{EEV})/z_{RA}$$

Here, z_{RA} represents the objective value obtained from the two-stage risk averse stochastic model, while z_{EEV} is the objective value when the stochastic model is solved with the first-stage decisions fixed to those derived from the deterministic model, where uncertain parameters are replaced by their expected values.

Figure 3: Change of VSS (%)

Figure 3 portrays VSS (%) against α for five $\lambda=0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75,$ and 1. In the risk-neutral case ($\lambda=0$) the measure is insensitive to α ; VSS settles at a single value of about 3 %, showing that a deterministic solution already captures virtually all the attainable benefit. Introducing a mild degree of aversion ($\lambda=0.25$) nudges that value upward to roughly 3.5 % but leaves the curve almost flat, so tightening the confidence requirement still yields little extra return. Raising λ to 0.50 lifts the baseline to around 4% and imparts a gentle positive slope, meaning that higher α now produces a modest increment in VSS. When $\lambda=0.75$, both the starting level and the slope increase: VSS begins near 4.5%

at $\alpha=0.70$ and rises to about 5.5% by $\alpha=0.90$, indicating that risk-conscious planners reap greater benefit from modeling uncertainty as reliability demands intensify. Under full aversion ($\lambda=1$) the curve is highest and steepest; VSS climbs from roughly 5.5 % at $\alpha=0.70$ to nearly 7 % at $\alpha=0.90$, underscoring the premium placed on stochastic optimization when both risk sensitivity and confidence requirements peak. Overall, VSS increases monotonically in both λ and α , and the marginal value of a stochastic solution is greatest where these two drivers reinforce one another.

4 CONCLUSION

The proposed CVaR-based stochastic programming framework demonstrates strong potential for the optimal design of hybrid multigeneration energy systems. By explicitly accounting for uncertainties in demand, renewable generation, and market prices, this approach delivers solutions that are both reliable and economically sound. The results confirm that incorporating risk aversion into the planning process leads to more resilient system configurations, capable of maintaining performance even under adverse conditions.

For future development, integrating machine learning methods can further enhance system capabilities. Techniques such as neural networks can improve the accuracy of demand and generation forecasts, while reinforcement learning can support adaptive, real-time operational strategies. These advancements will enable hybrid energy systems to respond more effectively to changing environments, driving greater efficiency and flexibility in sustainable energy management.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Gielen, F. Boshell, D. Saygin, M. D. Bazilian, N. Wagner, and R. Gorini, "The role of renewable energy in the global energy transformation," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 24, pp. 38–50, 2019.
- [2] IRENA, "World Energy Transitions Outlook: 1.5°C Pathway," Abu Dhabi, 2021.
- [3] European Commission, "European Green Deal: Commission proposes to raise the climate ambition and presents path to climate neutrality by 2050," Brussels, 2020.
- [4] P. Mancarella, "MES (multi-energy systems): An overview of concepts and evaluation models," *Energy*, vol. 65, pp. 1–17, 2014.
- [5] G. Chicco and P. Mancarella, "Distributed multi-generation: A comprehensive view," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 535–551, 2009.
- [6] A. Omu, R. Choudhary, and A. Boies, "Distributed energy resource system optimisation using mixed integer linear programming," *Energy Policy*, vol. 61, pp. 249–266, 2013.
- [7] M. A. Rosen and S. Koochi-Fayegh, "The prospects for hydrogen as an energy carrier: An overview of hydrogen energy and hydrogen energy systems," *Energy Ecol Environ*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 10–29, 2016.
- [8] H. Lund, P. A. Østergaard, D. Connolly, and B. V. Mathiesen, "Smart energy and smart energy systems," *Energy*, vol. 137, pp. 556–565, 2017.
- [9] A. A. Rentizelas, A. I. Tolis, and I. P. Tatsiopoulou, "Logistics issues of biomass: The storage problem and the multi-biomass supply chain," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 887–894, 2009.
- [10] I. Dincer and C. Acar, "Smart energy systems for a sustainable future," *Appl Energy*, vol. 194, pp. 225–235, 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.12.058>.
- [11] S. M. Poorseyed and A. Askarzadeh, "Risk-averse optimal operation of an on-grid photovoltaic/battery/diesel generator hybrid energy system using information gap decision theory," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 17, no. 11, pp. 2801–2814, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1049/rpg2.12801.
- [12] S. Mohseni and A. C. Brent, "Probabilistic sizing and scheduling co-optimisation of hybrid battery/super-capacitor energy storage systems in micro-grids," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 73, p. 109172, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.109172>.

- [13] J. Liu, C. Chen, Z. Liu, K. Jermstittiparsert, and N. Ghadimi, "An IGDT-based risk-involved optimal bidding strategy for hydrogen storage-based intelligent parking lot of electric vehicles," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 27, p. 101057, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2019.101057.
- [14] S. Nojavan and K. Zare, "Risk-based optimal bidding strategy of generation company in day-ahead electricity market using information gap decision theory," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 48, pp. 83–92, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2012.11.028>.
- [15] A. Kaabeche and R. Ibtouen, "Techno-economic optimization of hybrid photovoltaic/wind/diesel/battery generation in a stand-alone power system," *Solar Energy*, vol. 103, pp. 171–182, 2014, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2014.02.017>.
- [16] P. Beraldi, A. Algieri, and G. Lavia, "Optimal design of hybrid multigeneration systems to enhance sustainability in the residential sector," *Comput Chem Eng*, vol. 198, p. 109051, 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2025.109051>.
- [17] S. Nojavan, K. Saberi, and K. Zare, "Risk-based performance of combined cooling, heating and power (CCHP) integrated with renewable energies using information gap decision theory," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 159, p. 113875, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.113875>.
- [18] M. Sharafi and T. Y. ElMekkawy, "Stochastic optimization of hybrid renewable energy systems using sampling average method," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 52, pp. 1668–1679, 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.08.010>.
- [19] B. S. Pali and S. Vadhera, "A novel pumped hydro-energy storage scheme with wind energy for power generation at constant voltage in rural areas," *Renew Energy*, vol. 127, pp. 802–810, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.05.028>.
- [20] Z. Li, L. Wu, and Y. Xu, "Risk-Averse Coordinated Operation of a Multi-Energy Microgrid Considering Voltage/Var Control and Thermal Flow: An Adaptive Stochastic Approach," *IEEE Trans Smart Grid*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 3914–3927, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TSG.2021.3080312.
- [21] H. Lan, S. Wen, Y.-Y. Hong, D. C. Yu, and L. Zhang, "Optimal sizing of hybrid PV/diesel/battery in ship power system," *Appl Energy*, vol. 158, pp. 26–34, 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.08.031>.
- [22] R. T. Rockafellar and S. Uryasev, "Optimization of conditional value-at-risk," *Journal of Risk*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 21–42, 2000.
- [23] R. T. Rockafellar and S. Uryasev, "Conditional value-at-risk for general loss distributions," *J Bank Financ*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 1443–1471, 2002.
- [24] P. Artzner, F. Delbaen, J.-M. Eber, and D. Heath, "Coherent measures of risk," *Math Financ*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 203–228, 1999.
- [25] C. Acerbi and D. Tasche, "On the coherence of expected shortfall," *J Bank Financ*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 1487–1503, 2002.
- [26] G. C. Pflug, "Some remarks on the value-at-risk and the conditional value-at-risk," *Probabilistic Constrained Optimization*, pp. 272–281, 2000.
- [27] H. Zareipour, K. Bhattacharya, and C. A. Cañizares, "Electricity market price volatility: The case of Ontario," *Energy Policy*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 4739–4748, 2007.
- [28] J. Gotoh and Y. Takano, "Newsvendor solutions via conditional value-at-risk minimization," *Eur J Oper Res*, vol. 179, no. 1, pp. 80–96, 2007.
- [29] ARERA, "Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente (ARERA)," 2024.
- [30] AIEL, "AIEL- Associazione Italiana Energie Agroforestali ," 2024.